

Current technical and practical impediments to research on social robots

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Abstract. Social robots are increasingly gaining the attention of the research community. However, there are various impediments to using social robots within scientific research. Some of the issues concern their limited availability in the market, their high cost and the inaccessibility to reprogram them. This paper reflects on the current state of the field.

Keywords: Social robots, research, HRI, CRI.

INTRODUCTION

Commercial social robots are flourishing. A rapidly growing industry produces social robots, notably as companions for the elderly or as devices to teach or entertain children [1-2]. Researchers using social robots, however, still encounter several problems. For example, while many social robots are advertised, many of them are not yet available and remain on a “pre-order” status for a long time. Another key problem of using social robots in research is the price. Many of the currently available social robots are expensive and sometimes require pricey maintenance.

Apart from their lacking availability and high price, many social robots currently suffer from limited technical capabilities. Manufacturers of robotic platforms tend not to be sufficiently transparent about robots’ actual capabilities [3-6]. To get a somewhat more realistic impression of what social robots can – and cannot – do, researchers are thus bound to rely on videos on Youtube or other video-sharing platforms only. On the one hand, some of these videos can convey reasonably well how interactive a robot is, how smoothly it moves, and how easy it is to use. On the other hand, some of these videos can sometimes be misleading. They show impressive capabilities of the robot in perfect conditions with little noise and perfect light. Unsurprisingly, in such conditions key features of social robots, such as speech and image recognition, work impeccably under such circumstances. However, functionalities such as face detection, face recognition, object recognition, and human behavior understanding, can currently only be used in restricted scenarios [7]. In addition, speech recognition is still underperforming. Consequently, natural language understanding – a crucial aspect of human-robot interaction (HRI) – remains cumbersome and communicative HRI scenarios are limited [8].

A final problem of current social robots concerns the possibilities to reprogram the robot. In some studies, researchers may want to change the behavior of the robot (e.g., personalize an interaction in line with characteristics of the human actor). In that case,

researchers need access to the code with a Software Development Kit (SDK). Not all the commercial platforms, however, provide easy access to their codes. The resulting issues often consume a lot of time and effort.

THE MARKET

Against this background, we investigated the market in terms of different social robotic platforms and their fit to the necessities of our project. Our project, which is funded by the European Research Council (ERC) and conducted in The Netherlands, aims to develop an integrative framework of child-robot interaction (CRI). We study what predicts children’s acceptance of social robots; whether CRI affects the extent to which children learn social skills from social robots and form relationships with them; and which processes underlie such effects. Thus, we need a reliable, interactive, affordable, programmable, entertaining and robust social robot.

One of the most popular social robots is the NAO which has been used in many studies in CRI [9-11]. However, its price (>5000€), is a limitation when, as part of the project, an in-home study with many children is to be conducted. Other human-like robots such as Alpha 1 Pro [10] or Darwin-Mini [13] do not meet our expectations about autonomous behavior and their capacity of being reprogrammed. Moreover, they are not available with Dutch language abilities.

Other social robots that are about to enter the market turned out not to meet our expectations either. Jibo seems to become a popular robot for use at home. It can look, listen, and learn due to its artificial intelligence. It offers many interesting capabilities but it is currently only shipped to Canada and the United States of America [14]. The Zenbo robot [15], the Kuri robot [16], or the FURo-i robot [17] all seem to offer capabilities similar to Jibo, but are not yet on the market.

As available social robots are not suitable for our project and potentially suitable social robots not yet available, we focused on smart toys, defined as toys that “contain embedded electronic features such that they can adapt to the actions of the user [...] [and] process more information from a greater variety of sensors. This may include the use of microphones or speech recognition, cameras for detection of patterns and visual cues, accelerometers, proximity sensors, gyroscopes, compasses, radio transmitters, or Bluetooth for communicating between various parts to

[sic] the same toy” [18, p. 2]. We considered platforms such as Cozmo (170€), a robot with autonomous behavior, emotions, which is controlled by a mobile app with many capabilities [19]. We also looked at zoomorphic robots, such as Pleo, the dinosaur [20], and Chip, a dog robot [21]. However, all these platforms have their own limitations. Most importantly, they tend to look like toys rather than robots, are less interactive than social robots, and can be difficult to reprogram to meet the needs of our project.

CONCLUSIONS

Many different robotic platforms are currently available, but few can engage in a meaningful interaction with children (e.g., with good speech or emotion recognition). Moreover, many social robots are expensive and difficult to reprogram. Some technical universities build their own robot, but without such expertise, studies with social robots need to be adapted to the reality of the market. It is important that the current technical impediments on social robots are more strongly taken into account in strategies to advance the development of research on this field.

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